

Future directions in organic synthesis[†]

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In the beginning, all developments in organic synthesis centred mainly on elucidating structures of natural products. Slowly the emphasis shifted toward developing new reactions and methodologies to achieve total synthesis that reached its zenith toward the end of the twentieth century with more and more structurally complex natural products getting conquered by synthetic organic chemists. Meanwhile, new scientific developments, especially in the areas of spectroscopy, molecular modeling and biological sciences, have brought in irreversible changes in organic chemistry and drug discovery culture. The traditional methods of finding bioactive molecules from nature are being supplemented more and more with robotic high throughput screening of combinatorial libraries and structure-based rational drug design processes. The expertise gained over the years by the organic chemists are encouraging them to create new designer molecules that are expected to provide leads in discovering new drugs and materials.

The last century witnessed the golden era in organic chemistry when the art and science of organic synthesis flourished and reached a level of excellence manifesting its beauty and glitter endowed over the years by the painstaking contributions from the maestros of organic synthesis¹. The long journey from Robinson's tropinone synthesis, Woodward's strychnine, vitamin B₁₂ synthesis, Woodward-Hoffmann rules, Corey's retrosynthetic analysis and synthesis of hundreds of compounds to the present state of affairs mesmerised one and all². Development of new reactions, chemical transformations and novel methodologies contributed significantly in this epic journey. In the later part of the century, emergence of many extraordinary synthetic tools like, for example, Sharpless asymmetric epoxidation³, Evans' aldol reaction⁴, the concept of chiral pool and chiral auxiliary based synthesis made indelible impressions on organic synthesis and were instrumental in achieving the total synthesis of innumerable structurally complex chiral natural products in optically pure forms. Kishi's palytoxin synthesis⁵, Nicolaou's synthesis of brevetoxin B⁶, amphotericin B⁷, rapamycin⁸ etc. epitomise the breath-taking beauties and awesome complexities of modern organic synthesis.

We were swayed by the great surge of organic synthesis and deeply charmed as it helped to unfold many mysteries of the nature. We witnessed it playing pivotal roles in many discoveries in chemistry, biology, medicine and drug development processes. We were enthused to participate, whatever little way though it may be, in the stimulating exercise of organic synthesis. I have chosen a few representative examples from some of our own contributions in this fascinating area of research to show the state-of-the-art of present day organic synthesis.

An essence of the presentday organic synthesis

Studies directed toward the synthesis of amphidinolides⁹⁻¹⁵ :

Amphidinolides A-V constitute a family of structurally complex macrolide molecules isolated from the cultured marine dinoflagellate *Amphidinium sp.* Many of these compounds have exhibited extraordinary activities against a variety of tumor cell lines. Their structural diversities and potent biological activities have made them attractive targets for total synthesis. Though known for quite some time now, the total syntheses of only three members of this family, amphidinolides J, K and P, have been reported^{16,17}. As part of our studies directed toward the synthesis of various amphidinolide molecules, we have synthesized some key fragments of some structurally similar members of the family, amphidinolides B, D, G, H and L (1-5, Scheme 1).

Retrosynthetically these molecules can be divided into three major components (Scheme 2). It was envisaged that the top half segment **6** could be linked to the bottom half portion **7** through a 's-cis-1,3-diene' linkage **8**, before the macrolactonization could be attempted. It was essential therefore to devise schemes to carry out first the stereoselective syntheses of these key fragments **6-8**.

Synthesis of the top half in the protected form **9** is shown in Scheme 3^{12,13,15}. This could be achieved by joining two smaller fragments **10** and **11** by an aldol reaction. The aldehyde component **10** could be prepared in a straightforward way. During the synthesis of the methylketo component **11**, we developed an efficient protocol for the synthesis of chiral γ -hydroxy- β -methyl methylcarbinols starting from disubstituted olefins in three steps : hydroboration, oxidation and

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Scheme 1. Structures of amphidinolides B, D, G, H and L

hydride reduction¹³. In the first step, excellent regioselectivity was achieved with bulky hydroborating reagent 9-BBN, giving exclusively the 2-hydroxy product as a mixture of diastereomers, which were oxidized and hydride reduction of the resulting β -methyl methylketones with bulky reagent 9-BBN showed a general trend in favor of the desired *syn*-isomer. The protocol was applied successfully in the stereoselective construction of the C₂₀-C₂₆ moiety **22** of amphidinolide B starting from the *cis*-olefin **21**¹⁵. The Li-

enolate from the methylketo **11** was reacted with the aldehyde **10** to furnish the desired product **9** with 18*S* stereochemistry as the major isomer^{12,15}.

Scheme 4 delineates the stereoselective synthesis of the acetylenic precursor **24** of the bottom half **7** which is a common segment of amphidinolides B, D, G, H and L^{11,14}. Some of the key steps in this synthesis are the Sharpless asymmetric dihydroxylation and Nozaki-Hiyama-Kishi's Cr^{II}-mediated coupling between an α -alkoxy aldehyde **30** and a vinyl iodide **31** to get the *anti*-diol **33** from where the epoxy moiety is generated.

Synthesis of the C₈-C₁₈ fragment **8** of amphidinolide B is described in Scheme 5 in which the Stille coupling method was employed to construct the trisubstituted C₂₈=C₁₃-C₁₄=C₁₅ 's-*cis*-1,3-diene' moiety from a vinyl iodide **39** and a vinyl stannane **40**¹⁰. A fully functionalized vinyl iodide **46** was prepared from an acetylene precursor using Negishi's carboalumination/iodination method. The starting material for the synthesis of **40** was (*S*)-(-)- β -citronellol which was converted to a triol intermediate **54** in two different routes. Routine functional group manipulations gave the acetylene precursor **56**. Treatment of **13** with trimethylsilyl iodide (TMSI), generated *in situ* from NaI and TMSCl, in the presence of requisite amount of water, led to the formation of HI-adduct with internal iodide as the only product. The Li-anion generated from vinyl iodide was reacted with tri-*n*-butyltin chloride to get the vinylstannane **40**. Stille coupling of **40** and **46** gave the expected coupled product and finally some routine functional group manipulations gave the desired product **8**.

*Studies directed toward the synthesis of glycopeptide antibiotics*¹⁸⁻²⁰ :

Glycopeptide antibiotics of teicoplanin (**60**), vancomycin (**61**) etc. are widely used for the treatment of infections caused by Gram-positive bacteria and express their antibiotic activities by inhibiting bacterial cell wall biosynthesis by selectively binding to the C-terminal D-Ala-D-Ala residues of

Scheme 2. Retrosynthetic analysis of amphidinolide B

Scheme 3. Stereoselective synthesis of the protected top half of amphidinolide B (1)^{12,13,15}.

peptidoglycan precursor, muramyl pentapeptide²¹. Though many of these compounds have been known for nearly 45 years, only recently the total synthesis of vancomycin has been achieved²². As part of our studies directed toward the syntheses of glycopeptide antibiotics, several steps were undertaken to overcome the major hurdles associated in such syntheses. One of these is the presence of a large number of unnatural amino acids in these compounds, in particular α -phenylglycines which are among the most difficult amino acids to obtain in optically pure form. This prompted us to develop an efficient method for the enantioselective synthesis of optically pure α -amino acids using a diastereoselective Strecker reaction with α -phenylglycinol as chiral auxiliary (Scheme 6)^{18,19}. Available in both enantiomeric forms, this excellent chiral auxiliary is suitable for the synthesis of both L- as well as D-amino acids, the (*R*)-phenylglycinol being used for the former and vice versa. In addition, its facile removal by oxidative cleavage with lead tetraacetate under essentially neutral conditions makes it an ideal choice for the synthesis of α -arylglycines.

This has been exemplified by us by synthesizing for the first time the *N*-terminal fourth ring of teicoplanin, a 14-membered cyclic peptide where two α -arylglycines were constructed in optically pure form by employing our method²⁰. In fact, our method has been a choice and used frequently along with two other methods of Evans and William's in the synthesis of α -arylglycines during the synthesis of glycopeptide antibiotics²¹. It has also been used by many researchers for the synthesis of various other chiral α -amino acids²²⁻³⁰.

Radical-mediated opening of trisubstituted epoxy alcohols and its application in the synthesis of natural products^{9,31-33} :

The stereotriads of the '2-methyl-1,3-diol' framework, appear ubiquitously in various propionate-derived polyketide natural products. Recently, we have developed a method for the stereoselective synthesis of stereotriads 77-79 which involves opening of trisubstituted epoxy alcohols 73-76, prepared easily from the corresponding 2-methylbut-2-en-1-ols³¹.

Scheme 4 Stereoselective synthesis of the acetylenic precursor 24 of the bottom half 7^{11,14}

According to our study as shown in Scheme 7, both *syn*- and *anti*-epoxy alcohols, **73** and **74** respectively, on epoxide ring opening with cp_2TiCl_2 -cyclohexa-1,4-diene give *syn*, *syn*-diol **77** as the major product, whereas the products from epoxy alcohols **75** and **76** depend on the relative sizes of R_1 and R_2 . When R_1 is bigger than R_2 , the major product is *anti*, *syn* diol **78**. With smaller R_1 , the *syn*, *anti* product **79** predominates. Unlike the classical $\text{S}_{\text{N}}2$ -type hydride opening of epoxides where exclusive diastereoselectivity is observed, our radical-mediated reaction was feared to lead to the epimerization of the radical bearing centre. However, excellent diastereoselectivity was observed during the hydrogen abstraction process in all the cases studied by us. This was attributed to the possibility of the reaction going via a six-membered cyclic Ti^{IV} -intermediate, where the stereochemistries at C_1 and C_3 and the sizes of R_1 and R_2 were the deciding factors for the observed facial selectivity.

For 1,3-*syn* substrates, originating from epoxides **73** and **74**, the cyclic six-membered intermediate takes a chair-type conformation giving predominantly the *syn*,*syn*-product. The 1,3-*anti*-diols resulting from epoxides **75** and **76**, on the

other hand, comes from a twist-boat conformation where the sizes of R_1 and R_2 decide the stereochemical outcome of the reaction. In fact, it is the product stability here which probably decides the course of the reaction giving a thermodynamically controlled product. The C_2 -methyl possibly takes a position where it is closer to the smaller one of R_1 and R_2 with two dihedral angles of about 90 and 30 degrees giving products as seen in Scheme 7.

This method has been used by us successfully in our studies directed toward the syntheses of many natural products like amphidinolides **O** and **P** (**80**)⁹, cryptophycins (**81**)³², epothilones (**82**)³³ etc.

*Design and synthesis of rapamycin-peptide hybrid molecules*³⁴⁻³⁷ :

Macrocyclic immunosuppressants, FK-506 (**83**), rapamycin (**84**), cyclosporin etc. bind tightly to the immunophilins, a class of cytosolic proteins, forming complexes which in turn serve as ligands for other cellular targets involved in signal transduction. These naturally occurring immunosuppressants, thus, act as 'molecular adapters'

Scheme 5. Stereoselective synthesis of the C₈-C₁₈ fragment 8 of amphinolide B¹⁰.

to bridge, noncovalently, two distinct proteins together for biological action. This dual-domain model for the mechanism of action of these compounds poses significant challenge to structure-based design of analogous ligands. The first step toward designing an effective analog is to achieve an excellent binding with immunophilin. Recently, we have designed, synthesized and biologically evaluated two hybrid molecules **87** (Scheme 8) containing the rapamycin/

FK-506 binding domain and a peptide tether. Extensive molecular modeling studies were carried out to design these analogs. These studies were based on the assumption that the optimum length of the peptide tether should be such that it could lock the binding domain in that particular conformation, which is present in its FKBP12, the immunophilin for rapamycin and FK-506, bound X-ray structure. One of these analogs **87a** turned out to be best synthetic ligand

Scheme 6. Enantioselective synthesis of optically active α -amino acids. Application in the synthesis of *N*-terminal 14-membered ring 72 of teicoplanin^{18–20}.

developed to date for FKBP12 having an affinity for the receptor comparable to those of the natural products ($IC_{50} = 9.6$ nM).

Future directions in organic synthesis

The chemistry described above from some of the works carried out in our laboratory gives an idea to the reader about the current status of organic synthesis. Meanwhile, during the period when organic synthesis was being taken to the level of excellence, new scientific developments, especially in the area of biological sciences, have started contributing irreversible changes in organic chemistry and drug discovery culture. Today it is possible to find what causes a disease much faster than ever before. More and more organic compounds are being used to probe hitherto unknown biochemical processes involved in a disease. Increasing number of drug targets are getting identified, cloned and over-expressed. Their 3D-structures are being determined at much faster rates using modern sophisticated spectroscopic tech-

niques. These informations are harnessed to design new rationally designed knowledge-based molecular libraries. The traditional methods of finding bioactive molecules from nature are being supplemented more and more with robotic high throughput screening of combinatorial libraries and structure-based analog development processes.

To meet the growing demands for the development of new molecular entities for discovering new drugs and materials, organic chemists have started looking for new concepts to supplement traditional approach. The expertise gained over the years in the area of organic synthesis and the rational drug-design concepts are combined together, to create 'nature-like' and yet unnatural organic molecules that are expected to provide leads in discovering new molecules. Emulating the basic principles followed by nature to build its vast repertoire of biomolecules, organic chemists are developing many novel multifunctional building blocks. These building blocks are assembled rationally to create *de novo* molecules with beautiful structures and useful properties.

Scheme 7. Radical mediated opening of trisubstituted epoxy alcohols for the stereoselective synthesis of chiral 2-methyl-1,3-diols^{9,31-33}.

These new approaches will make valuable contributions along with traditional methods to enrich our arsenal of bioactive molecules to combat the increasing number of life-threatening deadly diseases.

Scheme 9 displays some representative examples of these designed molecules. During the total synthesis of cyclotheonamide, a thrombin inhibitor isolated from marine source, having an α,β -unsaturated- γ -amino acid, Schreiber got interested in vinylogous peptides **88** which show excellent helical structures³⁸.

Another class of interesting compounds called 'Peptoids' **89** was developed by Zuckermann and Cohen which are composed of polymeric *N*-alkylated glycines^{39,40}. They also exhibit helical structures which are reminiscent of those formed by some β -peptides developed by Gellman's and Seebach's groups as described below. Some peptoids also have useful properties. Cationic peptoids can act as DNA-delivery system and are reported to be more efficient than lipid-based DNA-delivery vehicles, which do not unpack well.

In recent years, Gellman's and Seebach's groups have done extensive work on β -peptides **90** which once again show interesting 'helical structures' which are slightly different from normal helices⁴¹⁻⁴³. Many of these compounds are also showing useful biological properties⁴⁴⁻⁴⁶.

There are reports on the studies on amide-linked oligonucleotides **91** where the normal phosphate linkages of oligonucleotides are replaced with peptide bonds⁴⁷. These molecules and Peptide Nucleic Acids (**92**, PNA)^{48,49} are finding useful applications in antisense-oligonucleotide therapies. Several modified PNAs (**93**) are also being developed⁵⁰. Eschenmoser's works on 'Homo-DNA' (**94**) or hexose-derived oligonucleotides are not to be forgotten in this context^{51,52}. On carbohydrate-based hybrid molecules, some of the notable examples are carbonucleotoids **95** by Nicolaou *et al.*⁵³, carbopeptoids **96** by Suhara *et al.*⁵⁴, and also other amide-linked oligosaccharides **97** reported by Wessel *et al.*⁵⁵.

From the examples shown in Scheme 9 it is clear that chemists are using the fundamental building blocks used by nature, like amino acids, sugars and nucleosides with intelligent manipulations of functional groups and bond connectivities to produce nature-like, and yet unnatural, *de novo* structural entities. Many review articles have recently been published in this new area of research⁵⁶⁻⁵⁸.

*Sugar amino acids in designing molecules*⁵⁹⁻⁶² :

Unlike peptides and oligonucleotides, solid-phase synthesis of oligosaccharides have not yet achieved enough efficiency for generating oligosaccharide-based libraries due to their structural diversities arising out of variations in their

Scheme 8. Design and synthesis of rapamycin-peptide hybrid molecules⁸⁷³⁴⁻³⁷.

sequences, position and configuration of linkages and heterocyclic ring sizes⁶³. If efficiently exploited these diversities can lead to astronomically large number of libraries since carbohydrates carry much more information per unit mass than do either nucleotides or amino acids. Carbohydrates also play very important role in cell-cell recognition processes. Many pathogens use carbohydrate-binding proteins to attach themselves to cell surfaces and initiate disease. Oligosaccharides and sugar molecules may have potential therapeutic values against many of these diseases. Combinatorial libraries of novel carbohydrate-based molecules may find many useful applications in new drug discoveries in the coming years.

Keeping in mind the growing importance of glycobiology and the problems associated in the synthesis of carbohydrate-based libraries, we envisaged a novel hybrid design represented by a class of compounds called sugar amino acids (Saa)⁵⁹⁻⁶². Sugar amino acids exist in nature as cell wall components in the form of neuraminic and muramic acids⁶⁴. They are also important structural moieties present in many natural products⁶⁵⁻⁷⁵.

Sugar amino acids are basically carbohydrate molecules bearing both amino and carboxyl functional groups on the regular sugar framework. The rigid furan or pyran rings of these molecules make them ideal candidates as non-peptide scaffolds in peptidomimetics where they can be easily incorporated by using their carboxyl and amino termini uti-

lizing well-developed solid-phase or solution-phase peptide synthesis methods. At the same time, it allows efficient exploitation of the structural diversities of carbohydrate molecules to create combinatorial library of sugar amino acid based molecular frameworks predisposed to fold into architecturally beautiful ordered structures which may also have interesting properties. The protected/unprotected hydroxyl groups of sugar rings can also influence the hydrophobic/hydrophilic nature of such molecular assemblies. In the last few years, extensive amounts of works have been done developing sugar amino acids as a novel class of peptidomimetic building blocks in generating desired secondary structures in peptides as well as in creating mimics of natural biopolymers⁷⁶⁻¹⁰⁴.

Scheme 10 depicts a novel reaction path developed by us for the synthesis of furanoid sugar amino acids **98** in which an intramolecular 5-*exo* S_N2 opening of the hexose-derived terminal aziridine ring in **99** by the γ -benzyloxy oxygen with concomitant debenzoylation occurred during pyridinium dichromate oxidation of the primary δ -hydroxyl group to carboxyl function, leading to the formation of furanoid sugar amino acid frameworks in a single step^{59,60}. This method was employed for the syntheses of two sugar amino acids, 6-amino-2,5-anhydro-6-deoxy-D-gluconic acid (**100**, Gaa) and its mannonic (**101**, Maa) congeners. Two more members of the family, idonic (**102**, Iaa) and a 3,4-dideoxyidonic (**103**, ddIaa) congeners were synthesized by

Scheme 9. Some examples of designed molecules in peptides and nucleotides³⁸⁻⁵⁵.

some alternate methods. Incorporation of these furanoid sugar amino acids into Leu-enkephalin replacing its Gly-Gly portion gave analogs **105-108**.

Detail structural analysis of these molecules by circular dichroism (CD) and various NMR techniques in combination with constrained molecular dynamics (MD) simulations revealed that two of these analogs, **105a** and **107a**, have folded conformations comprising of an unusual 9-membered pseudo- β -turn-like structure with strong intramolecular H-bond between LeuNH $\rightarrow$ sugarC3-OH, as shown in Fig. 1. This, in turn, brings the two aromatic rings of Tyr and Phe in close proximity, a prerequisite for biological activities of opioid peptides. The analgesic activities of **105a,b** determined by mouse hot-plate and tail-clip methods were simi-

lar to that of Leu-enkephalin methyl ester. The *syn* disposition of the β -hydroxycarboxyl motif on the sugar rings appears to be the driving force to nucleate the observed turn structures in some of these molecules (**105** and **107**). Repetition of the motif on both sides of a furanose ring resulted in a novel molecular design of sugar diacid, 2,5-anhydro-D-idaric acid (**104**, Idac). Bi-directional elongation of the diacid moieties of **104** with identical peptide strands led to the formation of a C_2 -symmetric reverse-turn mimetic **109** which displayed a very ordered structure consisting of identical intramolecular H-bonds at two ends between LeuNH $\rightarrow$ sugar-OH (Fig. 1), same as in **105** and **107**.

To further these studies, we decided to prepare a few more C_2 -symmetric peptidomimetics shown in Scheme 11

Scheme 10. Synthesis of furanoid sugar amino acids 100-103 and a sugar diacid 104 and their application in peptidomimetics^{59,60}.

and examined their structures and properties, especially HIV-1 protease inhibition activities, as these compounds structurally resemble many well-established C_2 -symmetric HIV-1 protease inhibitors. Conformationally constrained molecular frameworks of the 2,5-anhydro sugar diacid and 2,5-anhydro sugar diamines were used to construct architecturally beautiful novel C_2 -symmetric peptidomimetics 110-115⁶¹. Although none of these compounds showed any significant HIV-1 protease inhibitory activity, further refinements in design may lead to protease inhibitors based on these rigid carbohydrate-derived scaffolds.

Oligomerization of 6-amino-2,5-anhydro-6-deoxy-D-

mannonic acid 101 by solution phase peptide coupling methods gave oligomers 116-119 as shown in Scheme 12⁶². While most of the oligomers, in either protected or deprotected form, did not show any significant secondary structure, octamer 119 (P = H) exhibited a very strong positive band at 216 nm in its CD spectrum in MeOH and TFE, indicating the possibility of the presence of an ordered struc-

Fig. 1. Stereoviews of the superimposed average structures of various groups sampled during 100 ps MD simulations of 105 (top), 107 (middle) and 109 (bottom)^{59,60}.

ture in solution. Its ¹H NMR spectra in various polar solvents, however, failed to produce any distinct dispersion of the amide proton chemical shifts. Compounds 101 and 116-119 were found to be inactive in hypoglycaemic tests in rats.

Further work in this exciting new area of research is currently under progress in our laboratory.

Conclusions

I have tried to give an overview of the current status of synthetic organic chemistry giving some examples from our own work and a glimpse of the emerging new areas of research in organic chemistry where diverse structural frameworks are getting constructed and tested for their structures and properties. Maximum utilization of the potential of combinatorial chemistry and recent advances in this area will allow the fullest exploitation of the structural diversities of these designed molecules.

Sugar amino acids are fast emerging as an important class of multifunctional molecular scaffolds that can find wide range of applications. Besides being used in

Scheme 11. Synthesis of C_2 -symmetric peptidomimetics based on 2,5-anhydro sugar diacid and 2,5-anhydro sugar diamine⁶¹.

peptidomimetics as rigid templates capable of inducing secondary structures in peptides, the various functional groups on each of these sugar amino acids, specially their amino and carboxyl termini can serve as adapters for solid-phase synthetic methods providing opportunities to create libraries of multifaceted molecules that may emulate diversities of biopolymers.

This promises to be an exciting area of research for discovering new molecular entities¹⁰⁵.

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Scheme 12. Oligomerization of 6-amino-2,5-anhydro-6-deoxy-D-mannonic acid 101⁶².

Many sugar amino acid-based molecules are already showing encouraging results in various biological studies. They can also find useful applications as probes in understanding biochemical processes that cause a disease. The nonproteinogenic properties of sugar amino acids will make compounds having them physiologically more stable. Optimum utilization of the molecular diversities of sugar amino acids and the efficiency and speed of solid-phase chemistry will lead to the development of more and more bioactive

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